

Investigation of 1.5 kW secondary side power controlled method in a inductive wireless power transfer system

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ABSTRACT

The contemporary and utilitarianism of the existing consumer world is advancing towards the better world technical benefits in the electrical world such as wired phase to wireless phase utilizing its volatile features. This paper addresses the battery performance in constant current (CC), constant voltage (CV) through inductive wireless power transfer (IWPT) systems. To analyze this workable mode, the researcher has proposed the series-series (S-S) compensation topology which is load independent current output. While charging the battery through wireless, the coil resistance is found to be affected by the battery's current and power. To figure out a practical solution, the researcher has introduced novel closed loop bi-directional switches with duty cycle control. The existing theoretical and simulated results have been analyzed with 1.5 kW, 120 mm air-gap and 85 kHz frequency. In this connection, the researcher has self-developed a prototype to better understand the theoretical perceptions of the proposed WPT system.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The existing internal combustion engine (ICE) releases more harmful gases and creates unnecessary problems [1]–[4], it can be avoided by the electric vehicle (EVs) as the present solution. In that connection, there will be various charging standards like hybrid electric vehicles (HEV), mild hybrid, full hybrid, supercapacitor hybrid vehicles, and so on. For this reason, the usage of electric vehicles (EVs) dramatically increased [5]–[8]. The contact charging is not safer while charging the battery and heavy gauge cables are needed. The wireless power transfer (WPT) has many applications mainly biomedical implants, consumer electronics, and even electric vehicles, this approach can be advantageous since it does not require electrical contacts to transfer power [9], [10].

Several papers have concentrated on the design based on the coil alignment, power transfer efficiency (PTE), and performance. Devano *et al.* [11] analyzed the power transfer efficiency by using hexagonal coil arrays with misalignment status. Nafaa and Yonis [12] discussed the resonance condition in impedance matching to maintain the maximum efficiency while changing the coupling coefficient. Yamaghuci *et al.* [13] experimental design is discussed while changing the auto-tuning frequency. Alghairi *et al.* and Onishi *et al.* [14], [15] focused on an asymmetric 4-coil-resonance coupling module with multiple transmitters for high stability, maximum power transfer, and efficiency. Siddique *et al.* [16] presented an automated transmitter positioning system in a capacitive power transfer system (CPT). Shukor *et al.* [17] analyzed the effect of turn ratio, air gap length, and capacitor value at both primary and

secondary to voltage ratios with finite element analysis (FEA). Ouacha *et al.* [18] introduced a special algorithm for transferring maximum power to the wireless transfer system. Bosshard *et al.* [19] comparative evaluation of the current and voltage stress in the primary and secondary side components in the series and parallel compensated inductive power transfer system. Voglitsis *et al.* [20] proposed a bidirectional power transfer in the WPT system.

In previous literature, theoretical analysis, coil design, zero power angle, comparative assessments, and experiments have focused on transferring maximum power and higher efficiency. The secondary side power control and constant voltage (CV) or constant current (CC) are not well-researched in S-S compensation. For the charging of the battery, the secondary side power control and CV or CC are required.

The design of a secondary side power control with bidirectional switches by duty cycle control and maintaining the either CV or CC is more challenging compared with the basic topologies. The basic series-series circuit is discussed in section 2. The proposed duty cycle control in the existing model pulse generation is presented in section 3. The simulated results of a proposed WPT system are presented in section 4. Battery charging performance in CC mode in section 5. Laboratory set-up discussion in section 6. Last, the conclusions are drawn in section 7.

2. OPERATION PRINCIPLE OF S-S RESONANT CONVERTER WITH A BATTERY LOAD

Figure 1 shows the basic wireless electric vehicle charging structure. The transmitted coil is taking the supply from the grid and it is placed on the road also the other coil is placed inside the vehicle. Here the high-frequency full bridge inverter [21] circuit is used. To improve the maximum power transferred to the coil compensation is needed for both sides such as S-S, S-P, P-P, and P-S [22]–[24]. While using the compensation both sides reactive powers observed components are neutralized and transferred only to the active power also the transmitter and receiver voltage and current are in phase as zero power angle (ZPA) [25]. From that series-series compensation is simple and less complex to design [26]–[29].

Figure 1. WPT block diagram

2.1. FHA analysis of S-S compensation circuit

In Figure 2(a) such as equivalent model represents the compensation capacitance C_1 and C_2 and Figure 2(b) such as reduced circuit represents the voltage-dependent equivalent circuit. The coil resistance R_1 and R_2 , L_1 and L_2 , and M is mutual inductance. By applying KVL for the primary and secondary sides of Figure 2(b), the following primary and secondary currents can be written in the matrix formation in (1).

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{AB} \\ j\omega MI_1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_1 & -j\omega M \\ 0 & Z_2 + R_{ac} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where,

$$Z_1 = R_1 + j\omega L_1 + \frac{1}{j\omega C_1}, Z_2 = R_2 + j\omega L_2 + \frac{1}{j\omega C_2}$$

Figure 2. Basic WPT system: (a) equivalent model and (b) reduced circuit

From (1), we get the primary and secondary currents are I_1 and I_2 in (2).

$$I_1 = \frac{V_{AB}(Z_2 + R_{ac})}{Z_1(Z_2 + R_{ac}) + (wM)^2}, I_2 = \frac{jwMV_{AB}}{Z_1(Z_2 + R_{ac}) + (wM)^2} \tag{2}$$

In (1) and (2), Z_1 and Z_2 is the impedance of the primary and secondary sides, the mutual inductance representing in (3), the compensating capacitors C_1 and C_2 as in (4).

$$M = k\sqrt{L_1 L_2} \tag{3}$$

$$C_1 = \frac{1}{w_0^2 L_1} \text{ and } C_2 = \frac{1}{w_0^2 L_2} \tag{4}$$

At resonance, inductive reactance is equal to the capacitive reactance and neglects coil resistance in Figure 3. Apply the ohms law for Figure 3 we get the primary and secondary currents I_1 and I_2 in (5) and (6).

$$V_{AB} = -jw_0 M I_2$$

$$I_2 = \frac{V_{AB}}{jw_0 M} \angle 90^\circ \tag{5}$$

$$jw_0 M I_1 = R_{ac} I_2 = V_{CD}$$

$$I_1 = \frac{V_{CD}}{jw_0 M} \angle 0^\circ$$

$$I_1 = \frac{V_{AB} R_{ac}}{(w_0 M)^2} \angle 0^\circ \tag{6}$$

Figure 3. Resonance voltage-dependent equivalent circuit

Figure 4 shows the basic block diagram of the series-series compensation with an uncontrolled converter secondary side. The terminal shows the output of the inverter voltage V_{AB} and the rectifier input voltage V_{CD} . The (5) states that the secondary current is load independent [30]–[34]. The output power [35], can be found in (7).

$$P_{out} = P_{in} = Re(V_{AB}I_1^*) = \frac{1}{\omega_0 M} V_{AB} V_{CD} \tag{7}$$

Figure 4. Basic model of S-S compensation WPT system

3. PROPOSED TOPOLOGY AND ANALYSIS

Figure 5 shows the bidirectional switches S_5 and S_6 introduced before the uncontrolled rectifier with a closed loop system to control the output power and maintain the constant current by the duty cycle controlling method. After S-S compensation the voltage is a quasi-square wave, and then the Fourier series expansion [36]–[38]. Figure 6 shows $(\pi-\alpha)/2$ is the starting angle of the pulse, $\alpha=D/\pi$, D is the duty cycle. Let us take, 50% pulse width, the pulse on the period is 90° and the starting angle of the pulse is 45° . The V_{AB} and V_{CD} can be rewritten as (8) and (9).

$$V_{AB} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{4}{(2k+1)\pi} V_{AB} \sin((2k+1)\omega_0 t) \tag{8}$$

$$V_{CD} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} -\frac{4}{(2k+1)\pi} V_{CD} \sin\left(\frac{2k+1}{2}(\pi-\alpha)\right) \cos((2k+1)\omega_0 t) \tag{9}$$

Substituting (8) and (9) into (7), the output power P_{out} can be obtained as (10).

$$P_{out} = \frac{V_{AB} * V_{CD} * 8}{\pi^2 \omega_0 M} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\sin\left(\left(\frac{2k+1}{2}\right)\pi(1-D)\right)}{(2k+1)^3} \tag{10}$$

Figure 5. Secondary side power control WPT system

In (10), the output power depends on the duty cycle (D), inverter output voltage (V_{AB}), frequency (ω_0), and mutual inductance (M) kept constant. Figure 7 shows the inverter output voltage V_{AB} , S_5 , and S_6 switching pulse, rectifier input voltage (V_{CD}), and secondary current (I_2). These switches operate at double the resonance frequency and control the duty cycle accordingly output power was controlled but the input parameters were still constant. Total eight modes in one cycle, In the first interval S_5 and S_6 are in an off state, and the battery is charging through the supply, second and third intervals both switches are turned on, and the rectifier input is shorted this time battery is discharged through filter capacitor likewise total eight modes repeated the cycle.

Figure 6. Rectifier input voltage and inverter output voltage

Figure 7. Bidirectional switches operating waveform

4. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The values of the electrical parameters calculated in (11) to (17) are inserted in the Simulink model. The waveforms of the output voltage V_o , output current I_o and output power P_o as obtained through Simulink model are shown in Figures in sections 4.1 and 4.2, respectively.

$$L2 = Qs * \frac{R_{ac}}{\omega_0} = 6 * \frac{42.19}{2 * \pi * 85,000} = 474.22 \mu H \quad (11)$$

Where,

$$R_{ac} = \left(\frac{8}{\pi^2}\right) * \frac{V_o^2}{P_o} = 42.19 \Omega \quad (12)$$

$$L1 = \frac{M^2}{L_2 * k^2} = \frac{(62.9 * 10^{-6})^2}{474.22 * 10^{-6} * 0.16 * 0.16} = 325 \mu H \quad (13)$$

$$M = I_{srms} * \frac{R_{ac}}{I_{prms} * \omega_0} = 5.97 * \frac{42.19}{7.5 * 2 * \pi * 85000} = 62.9 \mu H \quad (14)$$

$$C_1 = \frac{1}{\omega_0^2 L_1} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{(2 \times 3.14 \times 85000)^2 \times 325 \times 10^{-6}} = 10.79 \text{ nF} \tag{15}$$

$$C_2 = \frac{1}{\omega_0^2 L_2} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{(2 \times 3.14 \times 85000)^2 \times 474.22 \times 10^{-6}} = 7.4 \text{ nF} \tag{16}$$

Quality factor and coupling coefficient can be found by (17) [39].

$$k = \left(\frac{1}{Q_s}\right) * \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{4 * Q_s^2}\right)} = \left(\frac{1}{6}\right) * \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{4 * 6^2}\right)} = 0.16 \tag{17}$$

Table 1 shows the coils structure is modeled with 3D ANSYS Maxwell software, by using those values simulating the model, for selecting the quality factor (Q) is 6 [40] is chosen for betterment of results. From Figure 8 can be observed that to avoid bifurcation-free operation is $k < k_c$, otherwise to get the two peaks of the frequency f_L and f_H corresponding to the output power accordingly to tune the circuit.

Table 1. FEM simulation coils quantities

Parameter	Values
Number of turns in transmitter	32
Number of turns in receiver	32
Coil diameter/mm	200mm
Self-inductance of transmitter/ μ H	325
Self-inductance of receiver/ μ H	474.22
Vertical distance varied/mm	120
Mutual inductance/ μ H	62.8
Coil	Circular
Frequency/kHz	85

Figure 8. Output power and frequency

4.1. Comparison of input voltage and current of the primary side and output voltage and current of the secondary side with the variation of duty cycle

Figure 9 shows the inverter output voltage (V_{AB}) and primary side current (I_1), Figure 10(a) shows the rectifier input voltage (V_{CD}) and I_2 at $D = 0$, the switch S_5 and S_6 are at OFF position is the same as an uncontrolled rectifier. Figures 10(b)-10(e) is the duty cycle variation from $D = 0$ to $D = 1$, the switch S_5 and S_6 are at ON, and the rectifier input voltage and secondary current can be controlled similarly the respective DC output voltage, current and power are changed but the primary side inverter voltage and current are not changed.

Figure 9. Inverter output voltage and current

Figure 10. Rectifier input voltage and current at a duty cycle: (a) $D = 0$, (b) $D = 0.2$, (c) $D = 0.4$, (d) $D = 0.5$, (e) $D = 0.6$, and (f) $D = 0.8$

4.2. Comparison of the output voltage, current, power and rectifier current of the battery side with the variation of duty cycle

Figure 11 shows $D = 0$ of the battery v_0 , i_0 , p_0 , and uncontrolled bridge current, where the switches S_5 and S_6 are in the off position. Figure 11(a) shows the battery voltage of nearly 300 V. Figure 11(b) shows the output DC battery current is nearly 5 A. Figure 11(c) shows the DC battery output power is nearly 1.5 kW, and Figure 11(d) shows the rectifier output current is the full wave.

Figure 12 shows $D = 0.5$ of the battery v_0 , i_0 , p_0 , and uncontrolled bridge current, where the switches S_5 and S_6 are in the off position. Figure 12(a) shows the battery voltage of nearly 200 V. Figure 12(b) shows the output DC battery current is nearly 4 A. Figure 12(c) shows the DC battery output power is nearly half, and Figure 12(d) shows the rectifier output current is the full wave. Figure 13, shows the simulated and theoretical power and duty cycle, while changing D from 0 to 1, the power is maximum to zero. Power is maximum only for D is equal to 1, which means both the switches are at off state, for power is zero at D is equal to one, both the switches are at on, get short-circuited, battery gets charged with the help of capacitor. Table 2 shows the duty ratio changing from 0 to 1, and the mathematical and simulated values of transferred power and efficiency are tabulated. Finally, the output power of the simulation results is the same as the calculation results.

Figure 11. Output of the battery at $D=0$ (a) output voltage (v_0), (b) output current (i_0), (c) output power (p_0), (d) uncontrolled current

Figure 12. Output of the battery at $D=0.5$ (a) output voltage (v_0), (b) output current (i_0), (c) output power (p_0), (d) uncontrolled current

Table 2. Theoretical and simulated power and efficiency varying the D

Duty cycle D	Inverter output voltage	Rectifier input voltage	Power/W		Efficiency	Conducting angle (α) $\alpha=D*\pi$ (deg)
			Mathematical	Simulated		
0	200	268.9	1353.28	1421	96	0
0.4	200	247.9	1094.83	1075	95.44	72
0.5	200	235.7	956.91	869.3	95.26	90
0.6	200	184.5	795.44	638.7	95.02	108
0.8	200	117.9	418.188	228	92.28	144
1	200	0	0	0	0	180

Figure 13. Output power and duty cycle

5. CHARGING MODES

5.1. Impact on the current and power while charging of battery with negligible coil resistance

Generally, in the design of the WPT systems, $\omega_0^2 M^2 \gg R_1$, and thus, the Secondary current is approximately constant with the variation of the load. By neglecting the R_1 and R_2 , (2) can be written as (18) and (19).

$$I_2 = \frac{j\omega M_0 V_{AB}}{R_1(R_2 + R_{ac}) + (\omega_0 M)^2} \quad (18)$$

$$I_2 = \frac{V_{AB}}{j\omega_0 M} \quad (19)$$

From (6) and (19): i) I_1 and V_{AB} are in phase, I_2 and V_{AB} have a phase difference of 90° ; and ii) The current of the secondary is load independent when the switching frequency is equal to the resonant frequency and the mutual inductance and the primary voltage are maintained constant but the primary current is dependent on changing of load see Figure 14 simulated and calculated primary and secondary currents. We can observe that the secondary current I_2 is 5.35 A is constant for changing of battery resistance from 10 to 80, but the primary current I_1 is varying. Also, the transferred power of the system is shown as (20).

$$P = \frac{(V_{AB})^2 R_L}{(\omega_0 M)^2} \quad (20)$$

Figure 14. Primary and secondary current varying with load

5.2. Impact on the current and power while charging of battery with changing of coil resistance

One issue that must be considered in the design of the circuit is that the resistances of the transmitter and receiver coils affect the output current and power. In CC mode, according to (18), if the battery equivalent resistance increases, the output current I_2 decreases, and the constant output operating is affected. The variation of the output current and power (20) versus the battery equivalent resistance for two different values of R_1 and R_2 are shown in Figures 15 and 16. It can be observed that the R_1 and R_2 are 1.1 ohms, the battery current is 5.439 A and 5.244 A, and the change in percentage is 3.718%, if the R_1 and R_2 is 1.5 ohm, the battery current is 5.329 A and 5.087 A, the change in percentage is 4.757%, also at the 50 ohm the variation for both is 5.439 to 5.329 A change in percentage is 2.06% and at 80 ohm the variation for both is 5.244 to 5.087 A change in percentage is 15.7%, this variation will be effected on the battery constant current operation also the affected on the power.

Figure 15. Variation of the battery current and battery equivalent resistance

Figure 16. Variation of the output power and battery equivalent resistance

In Figure 17 when the equivalent battery resistance changes 60 % from 50 ohm to 80 ohm, the simulated battery current I_{bat} only fluctuates by 3.7% from 5.439 to 5.244 A. During the process, the simulated output power ranges from 1479 W to 2200 W. The charging profile of the battery versus battery equivalent resistance variation is shown in Figure 18. It can be observed that in the figure while charging the battery the current variation is almost constant but the voltage is increased in the WPT system.

Figure 17. Battery current, output power versus batter equivalent resistance in CC working mode

Figure 18. Battery charging profile in CC working mode

5.3. Constant current charging mode under duty cycle control

Figures 19, when the load resistance decreases during charging, the current parameters and transmission power are changes in (19). The secondary coil current of the S-S compensation topology remains unchanged, while the primary coil current decreases accordingly. Considering the limit situation, if a sudden fault causes a short circuit at the vehicle side (secondary side) during charging, the primary coil current will be reduced to zero.

Figure 20 shows the respective simulation results in constant current mode with step change at 1sec the load is changed from 26 ohm to 52 ohm. Figure 21 primary voltage and current as well as the load voltage and current. The output current reference of I_o is set as 4 A. When R_L is 26 Ω and the transfer efficiency of active power measured in the simulation is 87.6 %, respectively. When R_L is changed to 52 Ω , the simulated I_o is approximately 4 A. And the transfer efficiency is 91.75%, respectively.

Figure 19. Transmission power varies with load

Figure 20. Simulation results of constant current charging mode under duty cycle control

Figure 21. Operation in CC mode with S-S circuit ($R_L = 26 \Omega$): (a) V_{AB} & I_t and (b) V_0 & I_0

Similarly, the primary current and voltage in CC mode with the battery equivalent resistance of 26Ω are shown in Figure 21(a). Furthermore, the current and voltage of the load are illustrated in Figure 21(b). As shown in this figure, the output current is 4 A and the output voltage is around 100 V. The current and voltage waveforms of the primary in CC mode and with the output equivalent resistance of 52Ω are presented in Figure 22(a). Also, the output voltage and current are shown in Figure 22(b). It can be seen that the output voltage is 240 V and the battery current is 4 A. During the CC mode, the current of the output is maintained constant at the level of 4 A when R_L increases from 26Ω to 52Ω .

Figure 22. Operation in CC mode with S-S circuit ($R_L=52 \Omega$): (a) V_{AB} & I_i and (b) V_0 & I_0

6. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A small-scale prototype is designed, for the length of both coils is 400mm×400mm, and the adjustable ground clearance. The transmitter side components are a programmable microcontroller circuit, high-frequency converter, compensation, primary and secondary coil, basic full bridge rectifier, filter capacitor, and load resistance. The prototype parameters are taken from Table 1 and the experiment prototype is shown in Figure 23. Figure 24 shows the gate pulse of the MOSFET switches of the inverter. The measured inverter output voltage and transmitter current have the same phase angle shown in Figure 25.

Figure 23. The small-scale prototype WPT charging system

Figure 24. Measured gate pulse of MOSFETs

Figure 25. Measured output of inverter: (a) current and (b) voltage

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new duty cycle control inductive wireless power transfer system has been introduced for the battery charging performance which was identified as a proposal. The S-S compensation is load-independent topology and it provides the CC charging. The important consideration is the coil resistance which affects the constant current and power of the battery. Another important consideration in designing that has been taken is the bifurcation effect which most of the IWPT charging designs have avoided. To avoid the above consideration, closed-loop duty cycle control is proposed and derived from the output power and duty cycle. Theoretical and simulated results have been observed, validated keenly, and proposed a small-scale prototype of the S-S compensation IWPT system.

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